

**The Science of Translating the Importance of Authentic Education
Across Linguistic and Cultural Borders from *3 Idiots* to *Nanban***

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Abstract

Cinema is a powerful medium for transmitting cultural values and societal critiques. When a successful film is remade, the challenge lies not only in recreating the plot but also in translating its thematic elements into a new cultural context. The film *3 Idiots* is a landmark in Indian cinema which explores the importance of authentic education and critiques the conventional educational system. Its Tamil remake *Nanban* offers a localized interpretation of the same narrative. Both films highlight the flaws in rote-learning, societal and parental pressure when it comes to education and career, the psychological pressure overtured by the institution as well as the importance of following one's passion. The paper studies how subtly *3 Idiots* is translated into *Nanban* suiting to the Tamil sensibilities while maintaining the original message without disturbing its thematic core and how both films address the purpose and value of education. This offers insights on understanding students' interest and passion is important for an authentic education.

Keywords: Translation, Remake, Authentic Education, Pressure and Passion

Introduction

The Hindi language film *3 Idiots* is directed by Rajkumar Hirani (2009) and the Tamil remake of it, *Nanban*, is directed by Shankar (2012). Both the films are excellent examples of how a story about education, societal expectations, and personal growth can be translated across linguistic and cultural borders. Despite both films revolving around the theme of authentic education and the pressure young people face in pursuing traditional definitions of success, they share the same core narrative. *Nanban* adapts the story for Tamil audiences through various linguistic, cultural and emotional nuances yet preserves the critique of the educational system.

The one that nurtures curiosity, creativity and critical thinking rather than rote-memorization is the authentic education that anyone could be offered. Both films follow three engineering students—Farhan, Raju and Rancho in *3 Idiots* and their Tamil counterparts Venkat, Senthil and Panjavan Parivendan (Pari) in *Nanban*. The character of Rancho/Pari, portrayed by Aamir Khan in Hindi and Vijay in Tamil, stand for the revolutionary approach to learning, one that is driven by passion rather than pressure. This character often locks horns with the Principal of the college, Virus, who is strict and rigid and he hates Pari for questioning him against his rules and discipline.

Literature Review

The Rote-based education system has been talked about extensively in many videos, magazines, news articles and so on where students are taught to memorize rather than to understand and their success is measured by grades which completely turns down creativity (Satyanarayana, 2023). The critique of the rote-based education system is depicted through the college environment in both the movies. One of the most intriguing aspects of the translation between *3 Idiots* and *Nanban* is the portrayal of the protagonist. Aamir Khan's portrayal of Rancho in *3 Idiots* is iconic, blending charm, wit and a rebellious spirit. Vijay's interpretation of the character, Pari, in *Nanban* retains these qualities but is filtered through Vijay's distinct persona, which appeals specifically to Tamil audiences. The subtle shift in characterization demonstrates the importance of cultural context in remakes. Despite the different portrayals, the core message remains the same where one should pursue learning with passion and not for external validation. Both characters symbolize the idea that true education transcends textbooks and examinations focusing on innovation, problem-solving and critical thinking.

The obsession with securing engineering and medical seats in Tamil Nadu has been a topic of concern and *Nanban* addresses this with much relevance. The competitive and rigorous educational environment may relate deeply to the pressure the film critiques. By depicting cultural aspects and the state's typical concerns when it comes to education, *Nanban* scores in making the message of educational reform accessible to a new audience without diluting the film's original essence.

Methods

Though *Nanban* is a faithful remake of *3 Idiots*, it also makes specific cultural adaptations to ensure that the story resonates with Tamil audiences. The paper engages in exploratory methods as Tamil cinema often emphasizes familial bonds and one significant aspect of the adaptation is the localization of character interactions, humor and the emotional moments to align with Tamil sensibilities. This aspect was well pictured in the translated movie in portraying Senthil's poor family background and his obligation to pursue a high paying job which heats up the emotional depth. This methodology paves way for a stronger underpinning of the study.

Analysis

In both *3 Idiots* and *Nanban*, the pressure of failure leads Raju/Senthil to attempt suicide, a poignant moment that underscores the tragic consequences of an education system that prioritizes grades over well-being. In both films, the institution represents a rigid system obsessed with producing successful, employable graduates at the cost of their personal well-being and intellectual curiosity. The films argue that this system is deeply flawed, advocating for a shift toward education that nurtures creativity, problem-solving and individual interests.

The character Virus, the dragon of a principal, represents the rigid and an authoritarian aspect of the educational system. He enforces strict rules, demands rote learning and measures success only by grades. His character embodies the traditional Indian educator, who prioritizes discipline and conformity over creativity and individualism.

In *Nanban*, the version makes Virumaandi a bit more relatable to the Tamil audience, who may recognize the archetypal strict principal figure in their own experiences. The film ensures that the essence of his character

remains a critique of a broken education system. The confrontations between Pari and Virumaandi in *Nanban* echo the struggles between individuality and conformity that both films address.

The character, Srivatsan is a conceited, tunnel-visioned student who is both insecure and arrogant. Obsessed with the race for top grades, teacher approval and academic success, he loses sight of real learning and personal growth (*Nanban*, 2012). Pari, on the other hand, studies engineering for his simple passion for machines and devices. He believes that one should follow excellence and not success as success will take care of itself if excellence is followed. In a specific scene, he challenges Pari and two other friends during their first year of engineering, betting on whose study approach will lead to greater success.

Srivatsan and Pari's two other friends go in search of Pari as he had disappeared after graduation. Later, they find the truth that Pari is completely a different man and Pappu is a boy at Pari's house who was passionate in learning. Hence, Pappu earned a degree in disguise for the real Pari. This emphasizes that a learning's value is greater than its certificate. To everybody's shock, they find Kosaksi Pasapugazh (their friend) a wanted scientist and as a revolutionist who had been transforming the educational system by starting a school in Dhanushkodi where students approach learning in a divergent manner. Thus, this paper encapsulates how authentic and a free-range education kindles interest students without pressuring them (*Nanban (2012) - Plot - IMDb*, n.d.).

Conclusion

In essence, *Nanban* succeeds as a remake because it manages to preserve the core message of *3 Idiots*. The importance of authentic education while making cultural adjustments that ensure the film resonates with Tamil audiences. The film addresses the broader issue of how education systems in India, regardless of region or language, often fail to nurture creativity and intellectual freedom. The pressures of grades, societal expectations, and the emphasis on traditional career paths like engineering and medicine are themes that transcend regional boundaries, making the message of both films universally relatable.

Through its careful adaptation, *Nanban* highlights the universal flaws of the Indian education system while also rooting the narrative in the Tamil socio-cultural landscape. By blending humor, emotional depth and a strong

critique of the conventional education system, both films offer a compelling argument for reforming education to encourage passion, creativity and mental well-being over rote learning and conformity.

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